

In-silico analysis to identify long non-coding RNAs as prognostic biomarkers in breast cancer

Ritika Bassi¹, Sahar Qazi¹

1. Health and Disease Laboratory, Quick IsCool, Aitele Research LLP

Keywords: lncRNA, breast cancer, biomarker, SNHG1

Abstract

Breast cancer is one of the most common malignancies after lung cancer which has become a public health issue on a global scale. Long non-coding RNAs have been demonstrated to play a significant role in breast cancer. Recently, lncRNAs are emerging as a novel promising biomarker for cancer diagnosis and prognosis. Previous studies revealed a significant level of expression of HOTAIR, GAS5, H19, UCA1, and LincRNA-ROR lncRNAs in breast cancer tissues. We performed an in-silico method for the identification of differentially expressed lncRNAs. Firstly, functional characteristics of the differentially expressed genes implied the presence of IL-6 expression, which can be an indicator of the metastatic stage of breast cancer. Next, the bioinformatic approach specific for lncRNAs revealed six seed genes; SNHG1, LINC00460, LINC00116, MIR31HG, UCA1, and NEAT1. Among these seed genes, SNHG1 had the maximum betweenness with the neighboring nodes and also had a significant AUC value >0.6 in ROC curve analysis, which makes it a predictive potential diagnostic biomarker. It was found that the transcription factors associated with SNHG1 were found to be involved majorly in transcriptional misregulation in cancer. Thus, this study will provide useful information to explore SNHG1 as a potential biomarker for breast cancer.

Impact statement

The major challenge with biomarker study is to distinguish between a potential and a reliable biomarker that can be used universally. For breast cancer, non-coding RNAs have been proven to be a potential biomarker. Thus, this study will provide good evidence for the altered expression of lncRNAs and their potential of being a reliable biomarker for breast cancer.

Aims and objectives

The aim of this study is to identify potential lncRNA biomarkers for breast cancer, for which these are the underlined objectives:

1. Perform transcriptomic analysis to obtain differentially expressed genes.
2. Enlist aberrantly expressed lncRNAs and construct regulatory networks (GRNs), which may act as suitable diagnostic and prognostic biomarkers in breast cancer.
3. *In silico* identification of major signaling pathways based on the footprints obtained from data (Gene set enrichment analysis)

The motivation

Breast cancer is a significant public health dilemma globally. It is reported as the most prevalent cancer which has surpassed lung cancer for the first time in 2020 (www.bcrf.org). Breast cancer development and progression are known to be significantly influenced by inherited, acquired, and epigenetic aberrations (Dumitrescu RG, 2018). Although the mortality rate of breast cancer has decreased over the years (seer.cancer.gov), it still has remained a significant clinical burden. As overall survival is good only if it is diagnosed at the early stages because it is considered potentially curable, one such challenge in breast cancer therapy is to identify novel reliable diagnostic and prognostic biomarkers.

Protein coding genes in the whole human genome are just 2% coverage, whereas the majority of transcripts are non-coding RNAs(ncRNAs). These non-coding DNA regions are found to be the hotspots for cancer-related mutations (Huang et.al, 2020; Cuykendall TN et.al, 2017). Where lncRNAs (>200 nts) were thought to be transcriptional noise but are now contributing significantly to mechanistic, functional, and translational aspects of cancer biology (Chandra G & Nandan T, 2017). Over the last decade, the advent of high throughput and next-generation sequencing technologies has contributed to genomic information and identifying novel lncRNAs.

Previous studies suggest that there are approximately 1,900 lncRNAs that are specifically involved in breast cancer (Sun M et.al, 2015), and their alternating levels may be associated with clinical outcomes. Dysregulated lncRNAs may function as tumor suppressors or oncogenes to influence breast cancer pathophysiology which should be investigated to better understand their functions in breast cancer biology and identify their usefulness as diagnostic and prognostic biomarkers.

The biomarker is defined as “a characteristic that is objectively measured and evaluated as an indicator of normal biological processes, pathogenic processes, or pharmacological responses to a therapeutic intervention” by US NIH’s Biomarkers Definition Working Group and the Biomarkers Consortium (ncbi.nlm.nih.gov). Studies suggest that RNA biomarkers have the potential over DNA biomarkers in that they offer dynamic insights into cellular states and regulatory processes. A cell can have many copies of RNA, which transmits more information than DNA (Xi X et.al, 2017). These RNA tumor markers will indicate the presence or progression of cancer and can be either found in body fluids or tumor tissues. Body fluid biomarkers, particularly those found in blood serum, are easily tested, and numerous malignancies have demonstrated their diagnostic efficacy (Lu C et.al, 2021). The first and only authorized lncRNA for clinical

usage at present moment is prostate cancer antigen 3 (PCA3), an early diagnostic biomarker for prostate cancer (PCa) (Groskopf J et.al, 2006). For breast cancer, Carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA) and cancer antigen 15-3 (CA15-3) have been approved by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) in serum. But these biomarkers have certain drawbacks, especially in terms of their poor sensitivity and specificity (Lu C et.al, 2021). Currently, serum MALAT1 has proven its diagnostic value for breast cancer with 83.7% sensitivity and 81.2% specificity (Zidan HE et.al, 2018). Therefore, the purpose of this study is to search for new molecular markers with enhanced diagnostic value.

Current status of Breast Cancer

Female breast cancer contributes 15% of the cases in support of which GLOBOCAN 2020 reported 22,61,419 incidence cases in 2020 worldwide. Out of these 0.1 million+ of the cases are contributed by India itself. Figure 1a displays the incidence and mortality rate ranking of breast cancer in Asia where India is ranked first, Figure 1b displays the estimated new number of cases in nations worldwide. According to the report, the number of incidences and mortality is expected to increase in the next 20 years.

(a)

(b)

Estimated number of new cases in 2020, breast, all ages

Data source: Globocan 2020
Graph produced: Global Cancer Observatory (<http://gco.iarc.fr>)

International Agency for Research on Cancer
World Health Organization

(c)

CANCERTOMORROW (IARC - All Rights Reserved 2023 - Data version 2020)

International Agency for Research on Cancer
World Health Organization

Figure 1: GLOBOCAN 2020 report. (a) Incidence and mortality rate ranking in Asia (b) Estimated new number of incidence cases of ovarian cancer in nations worldwide (c) Estimated number of cases and mortality of breast cancer worldwide and India expected from 2020-2040.

Results

Significant differentially expressed genes

After DEGs analysis, approximately ~7400 genes were found to be significant with p-value <0.05. Further, there were 3719 genes that showed log₂FC ranging between -1.0 to +1.0 with p-value ≤ 0.01. Out of these genes, many were over-expressed while some were under-expressed (Figure 2). Around 1600 genes were up-regulated, out of which 47 were annotated lncRNA genes. Figure 2 represents the volcano plot of all the DEGs based on log₂FC criteria. Whereas, 2000 genes were downregulated, out of which 44 were annotated lncRNA genes. The red colored dots represent over-expressed genes while the blue dots show under-expressed genes. The gray dots represent genes that are neither upregulated or downregulated in the case of breast cancer.

Disease-gene associations analysis

Disease-gene Association (DGA) approach helps to identify and signify genes that can be used as biomarkers for disease screening. All annotated lncRNA genes were subjected to DGA analysis in DisGeNET with input string = ‘(“breast carcinoma”) AND (“biomarker”) AND (“altered expression”)’. Out of upregulated genes, only 4 genes were falling in the criteria of selection which were LINC00460, LINC01116, MIR31HG, and SNHG1 and in downregulated genes, only 2 genes UCA1 and NEAT1 were identified. Table 1 below summarizes the description of these 6 seed genes.

Figure 2: Volcano plot of log2 fold change (FC) values of all significant genes.

S.no.	Seed Gene	Association type	Score
1.	LINC00460	Biomarker	0.01
2.	LINC01116	Altered expression	0.02
3.	MIR31HG	Altered expression; Biomarker	0.310
4.	SNHG1	Altered expression; Biomarker	0.02
5.	UCA1	Altered expression; Biomarker	0.1
6.	NEAT1	Biomarker	0.1

Table 1: Six seed genes from disease-gene association

Gene regulatory network construction, visualization, and topological analysis

For reconstruction purposes, we deployed OmicsNet using six seed genes namely- LINC00460, LINC01116, MIR31HG, and SNHG1 (upregulated genes); UCA1 and NEAT1 (downregulated). We applied the label propagation algorithm (LPA) to identify significant hub communities. The label propagation algorithm is one of the fastest methods used to categorize networks based on similar features. It is deployed to signify communities that share common or similar features (Malhotra D & Chug A, 2021).

Once LPA was applied to the networks, SNHG1 from the first network (Figure 3a); NEAT1, and UCA1(Figure 3b) from the second network were found to be influential and significant. Network topological analysis was also computed that consisted of betweenness, degree, and p-value of each 3 hub genes. Table 2 summarizes the network topology of the sub-networks obtained.

Functional enrichment of the associated genes was performed on the Shiny GO server (Figure 4). In Network 1, transcriptional misregulation in cancer pathways was found to be the most significant. Whereas in Network 2, module 0 represents the pathways that are involved in transcriptional misregulation in cancer and TGF beta signaling. On the other hand, in module 1, TNF signaling-related genes were involved.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3: Re-constructed network of seed genes (a) Network for upregulated genes (b) Network for downregulated genes

S.no.	Seed gene	Degree	Betweenness	p-value
1.	SNHG1	131	9035	4.54e-58
2.	NEAT1	197	21220	3.42e-70
3.	UCA1	36	2383	0.000763

Table 2: Network topology of the subnetworks

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 4: Functional enrichment analysis of network genes (a) Network 1, module 0 (b) Network 2, module 0 (c) Network 2, module 1

Receiver operating characteristics (ROC) curve analysis

AUC (Area Under the Curve) is a way to provide an estimate of the diagnostic accuracy of the test. In general, an AUC of > 0.6 is considered acceptable (Mandrekar, 2010). ROC curve analysis for chemotherapy of the TNBC (Triple-negative breast cancer) molecular subtype, which comprises 12-17% of all breast cancer (Foulkes, W.D et.al, 2010) indicated that SNHG1 expression is a potential diagnostic biomarker for breast cancer, with an AUC value of 0.704 (Figure 5).

Figure 5: SNHG1 ROC curve analysis.

Functional analysis

According to the results obtained, SNHG1 can be a potential diagnostic biomarker for breast cancer. Further SNHG1 was screened for Gene Ontology and KEGG analysis. It was observed that SNHG1 majorly was involved in RNA processing, nucleic acid metabolism, and cellular aromatic compounds metabolic process. According to the KEGG analysis, it was discerned that it has a role in spliceosome machinery, signaling pathways like Notch, TGF-beta, and certain pathways in cancer.

Figure 6: Functional enrichment analysis of SNHG1

Discussion

Many studies to date have revealed the roles of long non-coding RNAs in breast cancer invasion and migration (Gutschner et.al, 2013; Jiang et.al, 2018; Adriaenssens et.al, 1998), and also many of them have

been proved potential biomarkers like MALAT1. In the current study, using RNA-seq data from the GEO database, we identified 1630 upregulated and 2089 downregulated DEGs. Out of which lncRNAs were screened and it was found 47 upregulated and 44 downregulated annotated lncRNAs. Then, we performed disease gene association analysis which in result produced six seed genes which were LINC00460, LINC01116, MIR31HG, and SNHG1 (over-expressed); UCA1 and NEAT1 (under-expressed).

Then we utilized OmicsNet to visualize the relationship between these seed genes and transcription factors through the relational network. Subsequently, functional enrichment of the hub genes was performed in the ShinyGO web server which revealed that the genes are mainly concentrated in transcriptional misregulation in cancer and TNF-signaling pathways. Resulted hub genes were utilized to find the diagnostic power to be used as a biomarker with the help of ROC curve analysis. The analysis revealed SNHG1 had a significant AUC value, which predicts SNHG1 as a potential diagnostic and prognostic biomarker. In the end, functional analysis of SNHG1 showed that the enrichment of genes focused on RNA metabolic processes, spliceosome machinery, Notch signaling, and TGF-beta signaling.

Recently, many studies have unveiled the crucial role of SNHG1 in various cancer progression, proliferation, and invasion (Xu M et.al, 2018; Zhang Y et.al, 2020; Wang J et.al, 2018; Li X et.al, 2020; Li SJ et.al, 2019). SNHG1 has been reported to be upregulated in breast cancer, also high levels of SNHG1 are closely linked to reduced survival rates in breast cancer (Zhang M et.al, 2021). This was proved by the ROC analysis in this study, having the highest AUC score among all the predictive genes. It participates in promoting cell proliferation, migration, and invasion as well as EMT, which further affects the cell cycle and cell apoptosis in tumor growth. This is possible by activating certain signaling pathways like TGF-beta (Xu X et.al, 2018). This study will provide useful information to explore SNHG1 as a potential candidate biomarker for diagnosis, prognosis, and drug targets for Breast Cancer.

Methodology

Data Retrieval

The Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO), is a national repository of genetic information databases, including microarray and next-generation sequencing data (Barrett T et.al, 2013). In this study, we retrieved the expression profiling of GSE98393 by high throughput sequencing, which was specific for lncRNAs. This

dataset contained 15 different samples, subsequently out of which 9 were selected for our analysis based on the molecular and progression classification namely, the normal-like MCF-10A, HRAS-transformed MCF-10AT1 (early-stage), and MCF-10CA1a (malignant).

Data normalization, optimization, and pre-processing

Each cell line consisted of three replicates in a zipped Fastq format, with a single read. These files were transferred to the Galaxy platform (galaxyproject.org) for processing. Initially, the Fastq files were trimmed using cutadapt with a quality cutoff of 20 and a minimum read length of 20. The quality of the RNA-seq was then checked with MultiQC. The RNA-seq data was then aligned to the latest human genome reference sequence, GRCh38, as provided by the Galaxy in-built genome, using hierarchical indexing for spliced alignment of transcripts (HISAT2). It was followed by a quality check by MultiQC, to ensure good quality of mapping. Next, featureCounts was used to perform read counts, which generated count files for each dataset. It was also followed by a quality check by MultiQC. The package DESeq2 was then used to carry out the statistical analysis of differentially expressed genes between the breast cancer cell lines based on their molecular subtypes indicated above.

Differentially expressed genes (DEGs) identification

To eliminate redundant, erroneous, and noisy data, fold-change (FC) statistics and p-values were kept as the screening criteria in order to identify differentially expressed genes (DEGs) in cancerous vs normal samples. The cutoff criterion used was, $p\text{-adj} \leq 0.01$ and $\log_2\text{-FC} \geq 1$ (Upregulation); ≤ -1 (Downregulation). Additionally, ggplot2 in the R package was used for the volcano plot. Further, by using the NONCODE database (Lianhe Z et.al, 2021) we identified significant lncRNA and gene ids were annotated on g:Profiler (Raudvere U et.al, 2019). The list of these short-listed DEGs was further used in downstream analysis.

Disease-Gene Association analysis

Once DEGs were identified, they were subjected to disease-gene association (DGA) analysis using DisGeNET (Piñero J et.al, 2017). DisGeNET is a database that encapsulates numerous genes and variants that are associated with human diseases.

Reconstruction of gene regulatory networks (GRNs) and Topological analysis

For the reconstruction of the gene regulatory network (GRN), OmicsNet 2.0 (Zhou G. et.al, 2022) was used. This tool provided seed genes that were used for network module identification and visualization. Then, genes that were linked to these lncRNAs were used to predict significant pathways involving KEGG using the ShinyGO server (Ge S. X. et.al, 2020).

Diagnostic value of seed genes

The Receiver operating characteristics (ROC) curve is a graphical tool to evaluate the diagnostic power of a biomarker. It provides the relation between the sensitivity and specificity of a biomarker (Hsu MJ et.al, 2014). ROC curves were constructed using a ROC plotter webserver (Fekete JT & Györfy, B., 2019)

Functional analysis

Gene Ontology (GO) is a method that allows us to describe a gene/gene product in predefined classes based on their functional characteristics. In this study, we used a non-coding RNA Function ANnotation server (ncFANs) which is specific for annotating non-coding RNAs (Liao Q et.al, 2011).

References

- 1) Adriaenssens, E., Dumont, L., Lottin, S., Bolle, D., Leprêtre, A., Delobelle, A., Bouali, F., Dugimont, T., Coll, J., & Cury, J. J. (1998). H19 overexpression in breast adenocarcinoma stromal cells is associated with tumor values and steroid receptor status but independent of p53 and Ki-67 expression. *The American journal of pathology*, 153(5), 1597–1607. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-9440\(10\)65748-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-9440(10)65748-3)
- 2) Barrett, T., Wilhite, S. E., Ledoux, P., Evangelista, C., Kim, I. F., Tomashevsky, M., Marshall, K. A., Phillippy, K. H., Sherman, P. M., Holko, M., Yefanov, A., Lee, H., Zhang, N., Robertson, C. L., Serova, N., Davis, S., & Soboleva, A. (2013). NCBI GEO: archive for functional genomics data

- sets--update. *Nucleic acids research*, 41(Database issue), D991–D995. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gks1193>
- 3) Chandra Gupta, S., & Nandan Tripathi, Y. (2017). Potential of long non-coding RNAs in cancer patients: From biomarkers to therapeutic targets. *International journal of cancer*, 140(9), 1955–1967. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijc.30546>
 - 4) Cuykendall, T. N., Rubin, M. A., & Khurana, E. (2017). Non-coding genetic variation in cancer. *Current opinion in systems biology*, 1, 9–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coisb.2016.12.017>
 - 5) Fekete, J. T., & Györffy, B. (2019). ROCplot.org: Validating predictive biomarkers of chemotherapy/hormonal therapy/anti-HER2 therapy using transcriptomic data of 3,104 breast cancer patients. *International journal of cancer*, 145(11), 3140–3151. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijc.32369>
 - 6) Foulkes, W. D., Smith, I. E., & Reis-Filho, J. S. (2010). Triple-negative breast cancer. *The New England journal of medicine*, 363(20), 1938–1948. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMra1001389>
 - 7) Ge, S. X., Jung, D., & Yao, R. (2020). ShinyGO: a graphical gene-set enrichment tool for animals and plants. *Bioinformatics (Oxford, England)*, 36(8), 2628–2629. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btz931>
 - 8) Groskopf, J., Aubin, S. M., Deras, I. L., Blase, A., Bodrug, S., Clark, C., Brentano, S., Mathis, J., Pham, J., Meyer, T., Cass, M., Hodge, P., Macairan, M. L., Marks, L. S., & Rittenhouse, H. (2006). APTIMA PCA3 molecular urine test: development of a method to aid in the diagnosis of prostate cancer. *Clinical chemistry*, 52(6), 1089–1095. <https://doi.org/10.1373/clinchem.2005.063289>
 - 9) Gutschner, T., Hämmerle, M., Eissmann, M., Hsu, J., Kim, Y., Hung, G., Revenko, A., Arun, G., Stentrup, M., Gross, M., Zörnig, M., MacLeod, A. R., Spector, D. L., & Diederichs, S. (2013). The noncoding RNA MALAT1 is a critical regulator of the metastasis phenotype of lung cancer cells. *Cancer research*, 73(3), 1180–1189. <https://doi.org/10.1158/0008-5472.CAN-12-2850>
 - 10) Hsu, M. J., Chang, Y. C., & Hsueh, H. M. (2014). Biomarker selection for medical diagnosis using the partial area under the ROC curve. *BMC research notes*, 7, 25. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1756-0500-7-25>
 - 11) Huang, Z., Zhou, J. K., Peng, Y., He, W., & Huang, C. (2020). The role of long noncoding RNAs in hepatocellular carcinoma. *Molecular cancer*, 19(1), 77. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12943-020-01188-4>
 - 12) Institute of Medicine (US) Forum on Drug Discovery, Development, and Translation. (2009). *Accelerating the Development of Biomarkers for Drug Safety: Workshop Summary*. National Academies Press (US).
 - 13) Jiang, X., Zhou, Y., Sun, A. J., & Xue, J. L. (2018). NEAT1 contributes to breast cancer progression through modulating miR-448 and ZEB1. *Journal of cellular physiology*, 233(11), 8558–8566. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcp.26470>

- 14) Li, S. J., Wang, L., Sun, Z. X., Sun, S. J., Gao, J., & Ma, R. L. (2019). LncRNA SNHG1 promotes liver cancer development through inhibiting p53 expression via binding to DNMT1. *European review for medical and pharmacological sciences*, 23(7), 2768–2776. https://doi.org/10.26355/eurrev_201904_17550
- 15) Li, X., & Zheng, H. (2020). LncRNA SNHG1 influences cell proliferation, migration, invasion, and apoptosis of non-small cell lung cancer cells via the miR-361-3p/FRAT1 axis. *Thoracic cancer*, 11(2), 295–304. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1759-7714.13256>
- 16) Zhao, L., Wang, J., Li, Y., Song, T., Wu, Y., Fang, S., Bu, D., Li, H., Sun, L., Pei, D., Zheng, Y., Huang, J., Xu, M., Chen, R., Zhao, Y., & He, S. (2021). NONCODEV6: an updated database dedicated to long non-coding RNA annotation in both animals and plants. *Nucleic acids research*, 49(D1), D165–D171. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaa1046>
- 17) Liao, Q., Xiao, H., Bu, D., Xie, C., Miao, R., Luo, H., Zhao, G., Yu, K., Zhao, H., Skogerbø, G., Chen, R., Wu, Z., Liu, C., & Zhao, Y. (2011). ncFANs: a web server for functional annotation of long non-coding RNAs. *Nucleic acids research*, 39(Web Server issue), W118–W124. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkr432>
- 18) Lu, C., Wei, D., Zhang, Y., Wang, P., & Zhang, W. (2021). Long Non-Coding RNAs as Potential Diagnostic and Prognostic Biomarkers in Breast Cancer: Progress and Prospects. *Frontiers in oncology*, 11, 710538. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fonc.2021.710538>
- 19) Malhotra, D., & Chug, A. (2021). A modified label propagation algorithm for community detection in attributed networks. *International Journal of Information Management Data Insights*, 1(2), 100030.
- 20) Mandrekar J. N. (2010). Receiver operating characteristic curve in diagnostic test assessment. *Journal of thoracic oncology : official publication of the International Association for the Study of Lung Cancer*, 5(9), 1315–1316. <https://doi.org/10.1097/JTO.0b013e3181ec173d>
- 21) Piñero, J., Bravo, À., Queralt-Rosinach, N., Gutiérrez-Sacristán, A., Deu-Pons, J., Centeno, E., García-García, J., Sanz, F., & Furlong, L. I. (2017). DisGeNET: a comprehensive platform integrating information on human disease-associated genes and variants. *Nucleic acids research*, 45(D1), D833–D839. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkw943>
- 22) Raudvere, U., Kolberg, L., Kuzmin, I., Arak, T., Adler, P., Peterson, H., & Vilo, J. (2019). g:Profiler: a web server for functional enrichment analysis and conversions of gene lists (2019 update). *Nucleic acids research*, 47(W1), W191–W198. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkz369>
- 23) Sun, M., Gadad, S. S., Kim, D. S., & Kraus, W. L. (2015). Discovery, Annotation, and Functional Analysis of Long Noncoding RNAs Controlling Cell-Cycle Gene Expression and Proliferation in Breast Cancer Cells. *Molecular cell*, 59(4), 698–711. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molcel.2015.06.023>

- 24) Jalili, V., Afgan, E., Gu, Q., Clements, D., Blankenberg, D., Goecks, J., Taylor, J., & Nekrutenko, A. (2020). The Galaxy platform for accessible, reproducible and collaborative biomedical analyses: 2020 update. *Nucleic acids research*, 48(W1), W395–W402. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaa434>
- 25) Wang, J., Cao, L., Wu, J., & Wang, Q. (2018). Long non-coding RNA SNHG1 regulates NOB1 expression by sponging miR-326 and promotes tumorigenesis in osteosarcoma. *International journal of oncology*, 52(1), 77–88. <https://doi.org/10.3892/ijo.2017.4187>
- 26) Xi, X., Li, T., Huang, Y., Sun, J., Zhu, Y., Yang, Y., & Lu, Z. J. (2017). RNA Biomarkers: Frontier of Precision Medicine for Cancer. *Non-coding RNA*, 3(1), 9. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ncrna3010009>
- 27) Xu, M., Chen, X., Lin, K., Zeng, K., Liu, X., Pan, B., Xu, X., Xu, T., Hu, X., Sun, L., He, B., Pan, Y., Sun, H., & Wang, S. (2018). The long noncoding RNA SNHG1 regulates colorectal cancer cell growth through interactions with EZH2 and miR-154-5p. *Molecular cancer*, 17(1), 141. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12943-018-0894-x>
- 28) Xu, X., Zhang, L., He, X., Zhang, P., Sun, C., Xu, X., Lu, Y., & Li, F. (2018). TGF- β plays a vital role in triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) drug-resistance through regulating stemness, EMT and apoptosis. *Biochemical and biophysical research communications*, 502(1), 160–165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbrc.2018.05.139>
- 29) Zhang, M., Yang, L., Hou, L., & Tang, X. (2021). LncRNA SNHG1 promotes tumor progression and cisplatin resistance through epigenetically silencing miR-381 in breast cancer. *Bioengineered*, 12(2), 9239–9250. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21655979.2021.1996305>
- 30) Zhang, Y., Yu, R., Li, Q., Li, Y., Xuan, T., Cao, S., & Zheng, J. (2020). SNHG1/miR-556-5p/TCF12 feedback loop enhances the tumorigenesis of meningioma through Wnt signaling pathway. *Journal of cellular biochemistry*, 121(2), 1880–1889. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcb.29423>
- 31) Zhou, G., Pang, Z., Lu, Y., Ewald, J., & Xia, J. (2022). OmicsNet 2.0: a web-based platform for multi-omics integration and network visual analytics. *Nucleic acids research*, 50(W1), W527–W533. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkac376>
- 32) Zidan, H. E., Karam, R. A., El-Seifi, O. S., & Abd Elrahman, T. M. (2018). Circulating long non-coding RNA MALAT1 expression as molecular biomarker in Egyptian patients with breast cancer. *Cancer genetics*, 220, 32–37. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cancergen.2017.11.005>